

Vol. 12 | No. 2 | Jul - December 2024

ACADEMIC LIBRARY ASSOCIATION

ISSN : 2319-1392

IALA JOURNAL

(A Biannual Peer Reviewed Journal of Academic Library Association)

Vol.12, No.2

ISSN 2319-1392

Jul – Dec 2024

Editors-in-Chief

Dr. S. Srinivasaragavan

Professor & Head, Department of Library & Information Science,
Bharathidasan University, Tiruchirappalli.

&

Dr. M. Dorairajan

Associate Professor & Head,(Retired) Department of Library & Information Science,
St. Joseph's College, (Autonomous), Tiruchirappalli.

Published by

ACADEMIC LIBRARY ASSOCIATION

Tamil Nadu, India

CONTENT

S.No.	Title	Page No.
1	Faculty Awareness and Use Towards Scholarly Open Access - Mr. K. Marappan, Dr. C. Sivakumar	1
2	Assess the Accessibility and Usage Pattern of CMFRI's Open Access Institutional Repository - K.C. Anandraj, Dr. S Aravind	5
3	An Evaluation of "Open Science" Research Productivity: A Scientometric Study - Dr. S. Gunaseelan, Dr. M. Sumathi, Dr. C. Ranganathan	18
4	Reading Habits Among College Students in Thoothukudi District - Mrs. K.C. Shunmugapriya, Mrs. R. Ponselvi	29
5	Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Library Management System - Mrs. S. Meenambigai, Dr. J. Selvam, Dr. S.A. Sambathkumar	35
6	Global Information Access And Equity: In Open Access - Mr. K. Prabhu, Dr. R.Natarajan	41
7	Artificial Intelligence in Libraries - Dr. A. Ahila, Dr. S.A. Sambathkumar	47

An Evaluation of “Open Science” Research Productivity: A Scientometric Study

¹Dr.S. Gunaseelan, ²Dr.M.Sumathi and ³Dr. C. Ranganathan

¹**Librarian**, Central Library, AJK College of Arts and Science, Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India. E-mail: gunaseelan2703@gmail.com

²**Librarian**, Central Library, Shrimati Indira Gandhi College, Tiruchirappalli, Tamil Nadu, India. E-mail: sagusumathi@gmail.com

³**Professor**, Department of Library and Information Science, Bharathidasan University, Tiruchirappalli-24, Tamil Nadu, India. E-mail: cranganathan@bdu.ac.in

ABSTRACT

The paper analysed 2199 papers published in “Open Science” Research during the period of 2001-2021. Open Science is a set of practices that increase the transparency and accessibility of scientific research. It investigate the exponential growth rate, productive country, organizations, document type, language, productive institutions, productive country, top most journals, prolific authors, key words used and most cited papers. Scientometric methods were employed for investigation. Web of Science database was used for data retrieval. Results showed that there was an upward trend in the growth and development of publications on Open Science, the year of 2021 showed highest growth rate, journal articles are the dominant documents, university of oxford (UK) produced more publications, USA most productive country, journal of neurochemistry published more articles, Krumholz HM of Yale University the most prolific author, most cited paper are recently identified. The study is useful to LIS and Open Science researchers, faculty members and students.

Keywords: Open Science, Scientometrics, Highly Cited Papers, Exponential growth rate, Author Productivity

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Open Science

Open Science is the practice of science in such a way that others can collaborate and contribute, where research data, lab notes and other research processes are freely available, under terms that enable reuse, redistribution and reproduction of the research and its underlying data and methods. In a nutshell, Open Science is transparent and accessible knowledge that is shared and developed through collaborative networks ([Vicente-Sáez & Martínez-Fuentes 2018](#))⁷. Open Science is an umbrella term used to refer to the concepts of openness, transparency, rigour, reproducibility, replicability, and accumulation of knowledge, all of which are considered fundamental features of the scientific endeavour. In recent years, psychological researchers have begun to adopt reforms to make their work better align with these principles and to address the current “credibility revolution” ([Vazire, 2018](#))⁸.

Fig-1: Components of Open Science

1.2 Scientometrics

The term Scientometrics originated as a Russian term for the application of quantitative methods to the history of science. It is the science of measuring and analyzing

science. It includes all quantitative aspects of the science of science, communication in science, and science policy. Scientometrics is a application of quantitative techniques (system analysis, mathematical and statistical techniques etc.) to scientific communication (science output, science policy, science administration etc.) with the objectives for Developing science indicators; Measuring the impact of science on society; and Comparing the output as well as the impact of science at national and international levels ([Pouris,1989](#))³.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Garg and Ragulkumar Singh (2022) this paper analysed 699 papers published in Library & Information Science Research (LISR) during the period of 1994-2020. Google Scholar was used to obtain the number of citations received by these papers until April 30, 2021. The study examined the geographical distribution of published articles and also identified prolific institutions and authors. The study also examined the pattern of growth and identified the highly cited papers. Based on the analysis of data it is observed that maximum articles were published during the three years block of 2015-2017.**SafiqurRahaman and Yougal Josh (2022)** to examine the research productivity on big data in the field of library and information science between 2005 and 2022. It investigated the annual growth pattern, top countries, organizations, document types. Language, productive institutions, productive country, top most journals, prolific authors, authorship pattern, key words used, author key words, most cited papers and country collaboration. Scientometric methods were employed for investigation. The study is useful to LIS and Big Data researchers, faculty members and computer scientists. **SantoshChaturbhuj and NandkishorRamraoMotewar (2021)** the study is about the Scientometric analysis of published articles under the SavitribaiPhule Pune University, Pune since 2001 to 2019. Total of 6449 documents were studied. Specialisation Index and the Research Priority Index have been used for analysing the subjects and their sub-subjects Chemistry, Physics, Biology, and Engineering. The study provides an overview of research conducted by the University and tries to show the weaker and stronger areas in four major subjects. The study provides different ranking such as author's productivity, most cited authors, author's impact (h-index, g-index, m-index), most-cited journals and most contributed journals. **Sumathi and Ranganathan (2020)** this study reveals that Indian Scientists contributions of research papers related to the topic in Data Mining was undertaken from Web of Science Databases has been used to retrieve the data for 22 years (1999-2020) by the searching the keyword "Data Mining". The study reveals that, most of the researchers preferred to publish their research results in journals; as such 88.59%

of articles were published in journals further this study also identified to analyses source wise. Degree of collaboration, Areas of research concentration, word frequency, Geographical distribution of the literature and citation analysis is also noted

3. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The major objectives of the study are as follows:

- ❖ To identify the growth trends for research output of Open Science during 2001-2021
- ❖ To identify the most relevant sources and language of documents
- ❖ To assess authorship pattern and most prolific authors on Open Science Research Output
- ❖ To know the most productive organizations and countries
- ❖ To examine the top journals publishing papers on Open Science as well as the prolific authors
- ❖ To evaluate research themes and to find out the highly cited research papers

3.1. METHODOLOGY

The data for the study accessed from Web of Science database during 2001-2021. The researcher has used the search string “Open Science” for getting data from the Web of Science database which includes Science Citation Index (SCI). The data is downloading in plain text format and extracted with the help of R-programming and Bibexcel software. Further Analysis is done in excel software.

4. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

4.1 Main information about data

The present study has finalized 2199 research papers on Open Science research output, which appeared in 1005 sources between 2001 and 2021. Eighty four thousand five hundred in one references and 5310 author keywords were used to produce 2199 documents. The average number of citations per document was 16.61. Total authors are 12731. A single author produced 337 papers, while multiple authors contributed 12394 papers. The research paper per author was 0.173, while the collaboration index on Open Science research area.

Table-1: Main Information about data in Open Science Research Output

Description	Results
Timespan	2001-2021
Sources (Journals, Books, etc)	1005
Documents	2199
Average years from publication	3.33
Average citations per documents	16.61
Average citations per year per doc	3.625
References	84501
DOCUMENT CONTENTS	
Keywords Plus (ID)	4413
Author's Keywords (DE)	5310
AUTHORS	
Authors	12731
Author Appearances	15820
Authors of single-authored documents	337
Authors of multi-authored documents	12394
AUTHORS COLLABORATION	
Single-authored documents	381
Documents per Author	0.173
Authors per Document	5.79
Co-Authors per Documents	7.19
Collaboration Index	6.82

4.2 Exponential Growth Rate

The table -2 reveals the exponential growth rate of overall publications on Open Science during the study period. An exponential growth rate in number of publications was observed during 2001-2021. The highest growth rate (294) was found during 2021 with 722 publications, followed by (157) with 347 publications during 2019. The lowest growth rate (-3) was found in the year of 2013 with 29 publications followed by (-1) with 17 publications during the period of 2011 respectively.

Table-2: Exponential Growth Rate of Open Science Research Output

S. No	Publication Year	No. of Publications	%	Exponential Growth Rate
1	2001	2	0.09	-
2	2002	2	0.09	0
3	2003	2	0.09	0
4	2004	3	0.14	1
5	2005	5	0.23	2
6	2006	5	0.23	0
7	2007	6	0.27	1
8	2008	9	0.41	3
9	2009	12	0.55	3
10	2010	18	0.82	6
11	2011	17	0.77	-1
12	2012	32	1.46	15
13	2013	29	1.32	-3
14	2014	61	2.77	32
15	2015	71	3.23	10
16	2016	97	4.41	26
17	2017	141	6.41	44
18	2018	190	8.64	49
19	2019	347	15.78	157
20	2020	428	19.46	81
21	2021	722	32.83	294
			Mean	36

4.3 Document wise distribution of Open Science Publications

Table 3 shows the distribution of articles published in Open Science between 2001-2021. The maximum number of journal articles (62.8%) were published with 1380 publications, followed by reviews with 337 publications, and editorial material with 304 publications. By observing citation scores and cited references analysis, the form of articles has scored the highest values, followed by the source of review, editorial materials, respectively. Most often, the study suggests that the authors are more interested in submitting

research articles than any other type of submission, or that the journal allocates a set percentage of submissions to this category, undoubtedly due to the intrinsic value of qualitative research.

Table-3: Document wise distribution of Open Science Publications

S. No	Document Type	NP	Percentage	TCS
1	Article	1380	62.8	26017
2	Review	337	15.3	5854
3	Editorial Material	304	13.8	2779
4	Meeting Abstract	55	2.5	3
5	Article; Proceedings Paper	24	1.1	867
6	Article; Early Access	21	1	27
7	Article; Data Paper	15	0.7	268
8	Letter	15	0.7	65
9	Correction	10	0.5	11
10	News Item	10	0.5	1
11	Book Review	9	0.4	1
12	Article; Book Chapter	7	0.3	226
13	Review; Book Chapter	6	0.3	354
14	Review; Early Access	2	0.1	1
15	Editorial Material; Book Chapter	1	0	44
16	Editorial Material; Early Access	1	0	0
17	Reprint	1	0	0
18	Software Review	1	0	5
Total		2199	100	36523
NP = Number of Publication, TCS = Total Citation Score				

4.4 Language – wise Distribution of Open Science Publications

Table 4 indicates the language wise distribution of publications in Open Science which shows the publications were in 10 languages. English language is dominated with the stake of 2138 publications which is followed by German, Spanish and Portuguese with the stake of 20, 20, and 12 publications respectively. Remaining language publications have below 10 publications in Open Science. According to Citation Score analysis of languages English language have the highest citation score (36393).

Table-4: Language – wise Distribution of Open Science Publications

S. No	Language	NP	Percentage	TCS
1	English	2138	97.2	36393
2	German	20	0.9	61
3	Spanish	20	0.9	52
4	Portuguese	12	0.5	14
5	Czech	2	0.1	0
6	French	2	0.1	2
7	Italian	2	0.1	1
8	Croatian	1	0	0
9	Japanese	1	0	0
10	Slovak	1	0	0
Total		2199	99.8	36523
NP = Number of Publication, TCS = Total Citation Score				

4.5 Most Productive Organizations

The analysis of the table-5 indicates Institutional wise Open Science research productivity. It is noted that out of 2199 publications, University of Oxford (UK) had contributed 72 and McGill University (Canada) contributed second highest publications (71). It is identified from these analyses the highest citation score values are evident in University of Washington (USA) with 3250 citation score followed by University of California Berkeley (USA) with 2623 citation scores respectively. A keen observation of the table-5 it is identified that among top 10 institutions; the majority of USA institution has published more number of publications.

Table-5: Most Productive Organizations

S. No	Institution	Country	NP	Percentage	TCS
1	University of Oxford	UK	72	3.3	1219
2	McGill University	Canada	71	3.2	1002
3	Stanford University	USA	61	2.8	2018
4	University of Toronto	Canada	57	2.6	2408
5	Yale University	USA	49	2.2	1986
6	University of California Berkeley	USA	47	2.1	2623
7	University College London	UK	45	2	2020
8	University of Illinois	USA	44	2	1298
9	The University of Virginia	USA	44	2	2002
10	University of Washington	USA	42	1.9	3250
Total			532	24.1	19826
NP = Number of Publication, TCS = Total Citation Score					

4.6 Most Productive Countries

The geographical distribution of contributors is presented in the above table. USA is found that the highest contribution with 976 publications and also received highest citation score (23472) followed by UK ranked second with 430 publications and 9826 total citations. Germany stood third rank with 314 articles. Top ten counties and published above 100 publications received above 1000 citations

Table-6: Most Productive Countries in Open Science Research Output

S. No	Country	NP	Percentage	TCS
1	USA	976	44.4	23472
2	UK	430	19.6	9826
3	Germany	314	14.3	8197
4	Canada	290	13.2	7609
5	Netherlands	191	8.7	5356
6	Australia	187	8.5	5362
7	Italy	140	6.4	4306
8	Spain	129	5.9	3658
9	France	127	5.8	4276
10	Peoples R China	122	5.5	1756
Total		2906	132.3	73818
NP = Number of Publication, TCS = Total Citation Score				

Fig-4: Most Productive Countries

4.7 Scattering of Articles in Different Journals

Table 7 explains the top ten journals in different discipline of Open Science. The cumulated publications for the study period revealed that, Journal of Neurochemistry has highest number of publications with 52 papers which have received the highest cited reference (3330) followed by BMJ Open has next highest publications (51) and also received next highest cited reference (2097). It is identified the above analysis, Research Policy got the highest Impact factor (9.473) with 20 publications.

Table-7: Journal wise Distribution of Open Science Research Output

S. No	Name of the Journal	NP	H-Index	CR	NA	IF	Country
1	Journal of Neurochemistry	52	240	3330	395	5.546	UK
2	BMJ Open	51	121	2097	405	3.006	UK
3	Medicine	39	155	1663	297	1.889	USA
4	Systematic Reviews	36	68	1238	236	3.136	UK
5	Royal Society Open Science	26	59	1174	260	3.653	UK
6	Frontiers in Psychology	24	133	1122	99	4.232	Switzerland
7	Behavior Research Methods	23	148	976	104	5.953	USA
8	Language Learning	20	112	1348	68	5.240	UK
9	Research Policy	20	255	1603	42	9.473	Netherlands
10	Ecology and Evolution	14	83	782	74	2.91	USA
NP = Number of Publication, CR = Cited Reference, NA = Number of Authors, IF = Impact Factor							

4.8 Most Cited Research Papers on Open Science

The below table-8 indicates the highly cited papers on Open Science. Among the top research articles based on the citations revealed that, one of research articles which received more than 1000 citations of which the research articles entitled “The Astropy Project: Building an Open-science Project and Status of the v2.0 Core Package” published in “Astronomical Journal” stands with the first position and four of research articles which received more than 500 total citation.

Table-8: Most Cited Research Papers on Open Science Research Output

Title	Journal	Author	Year	TC
The Astropy Project: Building an Open-science Project and Status of the v2.0 Core Package	Astronomical Journal	Price-Whelan, AM	2018	1259
PsychoPy2: Experiments in behavior made easy	Behavior Research Methods	Peirce,J	2019	838
Environmental processes of the ice age: land, oceans, glaciers (EPILOG)	Quaternary Science Reviews	Mix,AC	2001	688
The Mass Production of Redundant, Misleading, and Conflicted Systematic Reviews and Meta-analyses	Milbank Quarterly	Ioannidis, JPA	2016	642
The preregistration revolution	Proceedings of The National Academy of Sciences of The United States of America	Nosek, BA	2018	588
The Psychology Experiment Building Language (PEBL) and PEBL Test Battery	Journal of Neuroscience Methods	Mueller, ST	2014	450
The NKI-Rockland sample: a model for accelerating the pace of discovery science in psychiatry	Frontiers in Neuroscience	Nooner, KB	2012	422
The death of the Job plot, transparency, open science and online tools, uncertainty estimation methods and other developments in supramolecular chemistry data analysis	Chemical Communications	Hibbert, DB	2016	382
The future of citizen science: emerging technologies and shifting paradigms	Frontiers in Ecology and the Environment	Newman, G	2012	365
Constraints on Generality (COG): A Proposed Addition to All Empirical Papers	Perspectives on Psychological Science	Simons, DJ	2017	351

4.9 Ranking of Prolific Authors based on Publication

The table-9 reveals that top 10 author based on publications of the subject of Open Science. The analysis reveals that, Krumholz HM from Yale University has 19 publications followed by Mohar D (Ottawa Hospital Research Institute) has got 14 publications, Ross JS (Yale University). Remaining Authors publications have below 10 publications in Open Science. Among the top 10 authors, Milham MP got 1062 total citations with 7 h-index followed by Nosek BA got 1020 total citations with 6 h index as the mark of quality of their publications.

Table-9: Ranking of Prolific Authors based on Publication

S.No	Author	Affiliation	H-index	TC	NP
1	Krumholz HM	Yale University	11	758	19
2	Frank MC	Stanford University	7	338	7
3	Ioannidis JPA	Stanford University	7	818	9
4	Milham MP	Child Mind Institute	7	1062	8
5	Moher D	Ottawa Hospital Research Institute	7	232	14
6	Ross JS	Yale University	7	411	12
7	Castellanos FX	New York University	6	1030	7
8	Griner E	University of Virginia	6	68	8
9	Nosek BA	University of Virginia	6	1020	6
10	Makel MC	Johns Hopkins University	6	122	6
TC = Total Citation, NP = Number of Publication					

4.10 Documentation of Keywords Appeared in Publications

Table 10 shows the top 10 keywords with strongest citation burst. Researcher finds out the keywords research history and items with research potential from them. The high frequency keywords are “Open” which is topped with 714 publications and first rank of the frequency and the total citation score is 10943. The next word that follows “Science” with 684 publications and 12037 total citations.

the year of 2013 with 29 publications followed by (-1) with 17 publications during the period of 2011 respectively.

3. The maximum number of journal articles (62.8%) were published with 1380 publications, followed by reviews with 337 publications, and editorial material with 304 publications. By observing citation scores and cited references analysis, the form of articles has scored the highest values, followed by the source of review, editorial materials, respectively.
4. English language is dominated with the stake of 2138 publications which is followed by German, Spanish and Portuguese with the stake of 20, 20, and 12 publications respectively. Remaining language publications have below 10 publications in Open Science.
5. It is noted that out of 2199 publications, University of Oxford (UK) had contributed 72 and McGill University (Canada) contributed second highest publications (71). It is identified from these analyses the highest citation score values are evident in University of Washington (USA) with 3250 citation score followed by University of California Berkeley (USA) with 2623 citation scores respectively.
6. The USA is found that the highest contribution with 976 publications and also received highest citation score (23472) followed by UK ranked second with 430 publications and 9826 total citations. Germany stood third rank with 314 articles
7. Journal of Neurochemistry has highest number of publications with 52 papers which have received the highest cited reference (3330) followed by BMJ Open has next highest publications (51) and also received next highest cited reference (2097). Research Policy got the highest Impact factor (9.473) with 20 publications.
8. Among the top research articles based on the citations revealed that, one of research articles which received more than 1000 citations of which the research articles entitled “The Astropy Project: Building an Open-science Project and Status of the v2.0 Core Package” published in “Astronomical Journal” stands with the first position and four of research articles which received more than 500 total citation.
9. Author Krumholz HM from Yale University has 19 publications followed by Mohar D (Ottawa Hospital Research Institute) has got 14 publications, Ross JS (Yale University). Remaining Authors publications have below 10 publications in Open Science. Among the top 10 authors, Milham MP got 1062 total citations with 7 h-index.

10. The high frequency keywords are “Open” which is topped with 714 publications and first rank of the frequency and the total citation score is 10943. The next word that follows “Science” with 684 publications and 12037 total citations.

6. CONCLUSION

The findings of this study will give researchers a glimpse into the contributions and advancements of the "Open Science" field, as well as point them in the right direction for future scientific endeavours. It would be interesting to revisit this topic in 5 or 10 years to see what has changed since this study was completed. The increasing availability of publication metadata, as well as the growing prominence of Scientometrics, tools, and techniques, opens up endless possibilities for future work.

REFERENCE

1. Bibliometrix. Available at <https://www.bibliometrix.org/home/> (Accessed on 29/08/2022).
2. Garg and Rahul Kumar Singh (2022). A Bibliometric Study of Papers Published in Library and Information Science Research during 1994-2020, *DESIDOC Journal of Library & Information Technology*, 42(1), 57-63.
3. Pouris (1989). A scientometric assessment of agricultural research in South Africa. *Scientometrics*, 17(5-6), 401-413.
4. Safiqur Rahaman and Yougal Joshi (2022). Big Data Research Publications in Library and Information Science: A Scientometric Analysis, *Kelpro Bulletin*, 26(1), 62-79.
5. Santosh Chaturbuj and Nandkishor Ramrao Motewar (2021). Scientometric Analysis of the Research Productivity of Savitribai Phule Pune University, *DESIDOC Journal of Library & Information Technology*, 41(6), 438-447.
6. Sumathi and Ranganathan (2020). Mapping of Data Mining Research Productivity in India: A Scientometric Analysis, *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*, 4367, 1-19.
7. Vazire (2018). Implications of the Credibility Revolution for Productivity, Creativity, and Progress, *Perspectives on Psychological Science*, 13(4), 411-417.
8. Vicente-Saez and Martinez-Fuentes (2018). Open Science now: A systematic literature review for an integrated definition, *Journal of business research*, 88, 428-436.